

Processing and Characterization of 3D Vascular Carbon-Carbon Composites

Henry Holman, Mark Olima and Dr. Michael Keller

Department of Mechanical Engineering, The University of Tulsa, Tulsa OK, USA.

C_f/C_m composites can be used in Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) receivers for power generation

Ivanpah Solar Power Facility in the Mojave Desert, CA [1]

Inconel 718 → Carbon-Carbon Composite

Illustration of molten-salt power tower with a thermal storage system [2]

C_f/C_m Composites have a better specific strength and Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE)

- Metals
- ★ Inconel 718
- Engineering Composites
- ★ Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics
- ★ C_f/C_m Composite

[3] Michael F. Ashby, *Material Selection in Mechanical Design*

[4] Cordeiro Jr, J. C., Zuzelski, M., Olima, M. H., Crunkleton, D. W., Otanicar, T., Ramsum, H., & Keller, M. W. (2024). Vascular Carbon/Carbon composites for concentrated solar power. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 108069

[5] Shi, S., Wang, Y., Jiang, T., Wu, X., Tang, B., Gao, Y., Zhong, N., Sun, K., Zhao, Y., Li, W., & Yu, J. (2022). Carbon Fiber/Phenolic Composites with High Thermal Conductivity Reinforced by a Three-Dimensional Carbon Fiber Felt Network Structure. *ACS omega*, 7(33), 29433–29442. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.2c03848>

Microvascular carbon-carbon composite with a straight channel

Micro-channel

CFD simulations in search for an optimal 2D channel geometry using ANSYS Fluent

Channel geometries with (a) 3 paths (b) 5 paths and (c) 7 paths

Input parameters	Metric
CTE (m^{-1})	4×10^{-6} , 5.75×10^{-6}
Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	3, 4.5, 6, 7.5, 9, 10.5, 12
Solar Flux (W/m^2)	750,000
Pressure Drop (psi)	5
Inlet Temperature (K)	473, 573, 673, 873, 973, 1073
Pipe Roughness (m)	3.2×10^{-6}
Absorptivity	.94
Emissivity	.88

CFD results: surface temperature and efficiency contours of different heat transfer fluids

Material	Density (kg/m ³)	Cp (J/kg*K)	Viscosity (kg/m*s)	Thermal Conductivity (W/m*K)
sCO ₂	49.31	1247	4.31E-05	0.09402
Na	801.7	1257.52	2.04E-04	62.5
KCl-MgCl ₂	1557.044	1010.2062	3.4627E-03	0.442

Multiple paths provide for a lower max surface temperature and higher efficiency

Successful fabrication of a polymer matrix composite (PMC) with 3D channels

3DHX samples had better flexural properties than 2DHX samples

Sample	P-value
Control vs 2DHX	0.0369
Control vs 3DHX	0.0847

Carbon-carbon composite fabrication is specialized

1. Prepreg

- Pitch carbon fiber
- Curing of phenolic resin
 - Up to 140 °C
 - 80 psi & vacuum
- Depolymerize at 260°C for 12 hours in vacuum

Autoclave curing

2. Carbonization

- Convert resin into carbon
 - Nitrogen atmosphere
 - 1000 °C
 - 1 hour
- Followed by intermediate graphitization at 2200°C for 1 hour

Quartz tube furnace

3. Densification

- Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI)
 - Methane
 - 1000 °C
 - Four 20 hours cycles

CVI in a quartz tube furnace

4. Graphitization

- Convert carbon matrix into graphite
 - Argon atmosphere
 - 2200 °C
 - 3 hours

Graphitization furnace

Carbon-carbon composite with 3D channel network

- 3D sacrificial catalyzed PLA template
- Cross-section of green part showing clear channels
- Graphitized 3D heat exchanger carbon-carbon composite

micro-CT images of the sample show clear channels and bridges

Clear bridges

Carbon/Phenolic Composite (pre carbonization)

Clear channels

Experimental setup to determine the pressure limit of the channels in the composite

- Argon gas
- FLOWERVE® Kammer Electropneumatic actuator with air-to-open action

The pressurization rig can achieve 1100psi with no leaks

Wu et. al. A review of research and development of supercritical carbon dioxide Brayton cycle technology in nuclear engineering applications. 2020

Higher fluid flowrates improved the effectiveness of the 3D channels as a heat exchanger

Average Surface Temperature of Composite Sample after Water Cooling Via 3D Micro Vascular Channels vs Time

Cooling Rate of Surface of Sample (Degrees C/min) vs Flowrate (mL/min)

Manufactured vascular carbon-carbon composite sustained 800 PSI without failure

Leak at the tube and channel interface

Summary

- Ability to manufacture Carbon-Carbon Composite heat exchanger
- Demonstrate effectiveness of a 3D cooling network up to 19 °C/min
- Channel structure can handle up to xxx psi

Future work

- Use different mediums like Helium or sCO₂
- Optimize channel architecture for better thermal and mechanical performance using FEA

Acknowledgments

Research Group Professor

- Dr. Michael Keller

Research Group Colleague

- Mark Olima

Questions?

Heat-pipe-cooled leading edge. Molybdenum-Rhenium embedded in C_f/C_m

Glass, David. "Ceramic matrix composite (CMC) thermal protection systems (TPS) and hot structures for hypersonic vehicles." *15th AIAA international space planes and hypersonic systems and technologies conference*. 2008.